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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Wireless Propagation Modeling Through Bayesian Networks

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ABSTRACT Over the last three decades, cellular network planning has evolved as a discipline in response to the ever-increasing complexity of mobile telephony. One of the key inputs to coverage planning, a central stage of the cellular network planning process, is the channel propagation model. This encompasses the main sources of degradation experienced by a signal in its way from transmitter to receiver. Currently, various well-known empirical models are used to estimate propagation losses in different environments. However, these mathematical models have been obtained by inference from measurements taken at specific locations, and generally their predictions do not match actual measurements obtained in other locations. Even worse, typically such predictions are not mutually consistent. To manage this uncertainty in terms of probability estimates rather than predictions, in this paper we propose a machine learning approach that is based on training a Bayesian network model from virtual data generated by sampling several empirical models. As a first step towards this initiative, we start by developing a Bayesian network driven by three well-known empirical propagation models, in their versions for urban environments: Okumura-Hata, COST 231 Walfish-Ikegami and Lee, which allow us to compare them in terms of probability estimations.

INDEX TERMS Bayesian network, cellular network planning, path loss, propagation model, urban environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

As stated in [44], cell planning (CP) is the most important phase in the life cycle of cellular systems, as it determines both operational costs and long-term performance. CP is a non-trivial process with many inputs, outputs, and trade-off situations, whose mathematical formulation can give rise to different optimization problems with different levels of complexity depending on the criteria adopted. Traffic model, potential site locations and propagation model are among the main inputs. The present paper focuses on the wireless propagation model. It is essential that the propagation model captures the main sources of signal degradation, namely path loss, absorption, shadowing, multi-path fading and even atmospheric phenomena. Hence, it is not surprising that intensive research efforts have been devoted to the

development of wireless propagation models over the past years. In particular, the new scenarios foreseen by current and future generations of cellular networks, as well as the growing number of high-performance wireless services, demand more reliable predictions of channel losses and, consequently, very powerful propagation models. In fact, an intense research activity is currently devoted to the characterization of wireless propagation in the millimeter frequency band where 5G/6G mobile networks are expected to operate.

A subset of propagation models is based on ray-tracing techniques [43]. Another subset is constituted by propagation maps obtained from actual measurements over the deployment areas [43]. However, ray-tracing and propagation maps are complex and highly time-consuming tasks, especially for large areas. In fact, the most successful alternative today is the use of empirical models, although the above-mentioned alternatives are currently re-emerging in the context of millimeter wave propagation.

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An empirical model is also based on actual measurements, but instead of representing them on a propagation map, they are used to infer a mathematical expression. In other words, empirical models abstract experimental and statistical data in the form of deterministic expressions, which are then used to make predictions in locations and regions other than those where the measurements were taken. As expected, usually these predictions do not match actual measurements in new deployment scenarios. Furthermore, the predictions obtained from different empirical models are not mutually consistent. To manage this uncertainty in terms of probability estimates rather than predictions, in this paper we propose a machine learning approach that is based on training a Bayesian network (BN) from virtual data generated by sampling several empirical models. The use of a BN not only provides a graphical view of the interaction between the intervening variables, but it also allows us to quantify, in a statistical sense, the influence of some of them on others. As a first step towards this initiative, in this paper we start by developing a BN model driven by three baseline empirical propagation models, in their versions for urban environments: Okumura-Hata [14], [31], COST 231 Walfish-Ikegami [7] and Lee [20].

According to [15], BNs first became a popular representation for encoding expert knowledge, while later several methods were developed for learning BNs from the combination of prior knowledge and data. This is the so-called Bayesian approach, which in general produces one or more BNs. Generally speaking, BNs can be viewed as a powerful artificial intelligence (AI) tool that can be applied to modeling systems where the input is a mix of incomplete data and prior expert knowledge. Usually, expert knowledge may take the form of causal relationships between variables, which are very easy to capture in the graphical representation of BNs. Furthermore, BNs include a conditional probability distribution in each node obtained from data. Note that an empirical propagation model also represents causal relationships between input and output variables, but these relationships are deterministically quantified on the basis of actual data. In contrast, a BN representing one or several empirical models is essentially a probabilistic formulation of the uncertainty associated with the predictions generated by these models.

Prior work on the use of machine learning (ML) tools to model the behavior of the wireless channel has mostly relied on artificial neural networks (ANNs), and also on various non-ANN alternatives, such as support vector machines (SVMs), genetic algorithms (GAs), k -nearest neighbors (k -NN), random forests (RF), boosting, etc. Good compendiums on the development of ML techniques for propagation modeling can be found in [6], [38]. However, despite the parallelism pointed out between BNs and empirical models, and the advantages of BNs over ANNs in terms of ease of understanding and interpretation, accuracy and model construction time, there is hardly any reference to BN applied to wireless propagation modeling. In a broader sense,

we can find some applications of BN modeling to other areas within the context of wireless networks: localization [10], anomaly prediction in aerial ad-hoc networks [45], reliability prediction [16], [39], prediction of mobile user throughput in 5G scenarios [24], antenna design [1], context extraction from wireless sensor data [26], wireless local area network planning and performance evaluation [2] and cognitive control of multi-hop wireless networks [33]. This paper aims to fill the existing gap in the application of the BN approach to wireless propagation channel modeling. In fact, to the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first to address this issue.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the concept of a Bayesian network is recalled. Section III describes the methodology followed in this paper to build a BN from the virtual data generated by sampling the aforementioned empirical models. Section IV shows the results obtained when making inferences from the calculated BN. Section V discusses these results and, finally, in Section VI, the main conclusions and suggestions for further research are drawn.

II. BAYESIAN NETWORKS

Models based on BNs [12], [18], [32] are characterized by their ability to capture potential relationships between features (factors), as understood by an expert [9], using a directed acyclic graph (DAG) where nodes have associated conditional probability tables. They constitute an established framework and an efficient reasoning tool for uncertainty management in Artificial Intelligence (AI), which have been used to discover the relationships between variables in the form of direct and indirect dependencies [12], [13]. Then, these dependencies are formally described by a graphical paradigm that combines graph theory and probability theory [19], [25]. BNs are specially selected because of their capacity to generate probability estimates rather than predictions. In this sense, BNs can help CP engineers to obtain path loss estimates from a probability network that can be continuously updated according to new information provided by engineers themselves.

Formally, a BN \mathcal{B} encodes a joint probability distribution P over a vector of random variables (features) $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, \dots, X_n)$ [18], [32]. It consists of [17]:

- A DAG \mathcal{G} , where variables are represented as a set of vertices (i.e. nodes), and interactions between variables are represented as a set of directed edges (i.e. arcs). Moreover, each variable has a finite set of mutually exclusive states.
- A set of local parameters \mathcal{P} according to the structure \mathcal{G} , where such parameters are the conditional probability distributions of each variable given different value combinations of their parent nodes.

Accordingly, the Bayesian network \mathcal{B} can be formulated as $\mathcal{B} = (\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{P})$.

The joint probability distribution P encoded by the BN \mathcal{B} is factored as a product of several local conditional distributions, which determine the dependence/independence structure of the DAG:

$$P(X_1, \dots, X_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(X_i | pa(X_i^{\mathcal{G}})). \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) is also referred to as the *chain rule for BNs*, where $pa(X_i^{\mathcal{G}})$ denotes the parent nodes of X_i in DAG \mathcal{G} . It is the main reason for the formulation of a multivariate distribution as a BN.

III. METHODOLOGY

Next, we describe the various aspects of the methodology followed in this paper.

A. DATA COLLECTION AND DEFINITION OF VARIABLES

To generate the proposed BN, we first constructed a dataset composed of all the variables involved in the urban versions of the following path loss models: Okumura-Hata, Lee (Philadelphia, Newark, and Tokyo cases), and COST 231-Walfish Ikegami. A subset of four input variables was common for all models: Hbs (base station antenna height, in meters), Hms (mobile station antenna height, in meters), d (distance from base station, in kilometers), and f (carrier frequency, in megahertz). Two additional input variables were required by the COST 231-Walfish Ikegami model, namely b (distance between buildings, in meters) and nf (average number of floors per building). Together with the output variables corresponding to the five path loss calculations, the dataset consisted of a total number of 11 variables organized by columns. Then, we generated each row by randomly sampling each input variable according to a uniform distribution, and introducing the resulting path losses. In total, we randomly generated 10,000 observations. Below, for the sake of completeness, we recall the mathematical expressions of the propagation models considered in this paper:

- Okumura-Hata model for small and medium-size cities [14]:

$$LU = 69.55 + 26.16 \log_{10} f - 13.82 \log_{10} Hbs - a(Hms) + (44.9 - 6.55 \log_{10} Hbs) \log_{10} d \quad (2)$$

In this expression, $a(Hms)$ is:

$$a(Hms) = 0.8 + (1.1 \log_{10} f - 0.7)Hms - 1.56 \log_{10} f \quad (3)$$

- Lee models for urban areas [20]:

(i) Philadelphia:

$$102.49 + 36.8 \log d + 10n \cdot \log \left(\frac{f}{900} \right) - \alpha \quad (4)$$

(ii) Newark:

$$95.20 + 43.1 \log d + 10n \cdot \log \left(\frac{f}{900} \right) - \alpha \quad (5)$$

(iii) Tokyo:

$$117.77 + 30.5 \log d + 10n \cdot \log \left(\frac{f}{900} \right) - \alpha \quad (6)$$

In the three cases, $n = 3$ for $f > 450$ MHz and:

$$\alpha = 20 \log \left(\frac{Hbs}{30.48} \right) + 10 \cdot \log \left(\frac{Hms}{3} \right) - 10.3 \quad (7)$$

This equation also assumes that $Hms < 5$ m.

- COST 231-Walfish-Ikegami model [7]:

$$PL = \begin{cases} PL_0 + L_{rts} + L_{msd} & L_{rts} + L_{msd} > 0 \\ PL_0 & L_{rts} + L_{msd} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here, PL_0 is the free-space path loss, formulated as:

$$PL_0 = 32.4 + 20 \log d + 20 \log f \quad (9)$$

Ikegami derived the diffraction loss L_{rts} as:

$$L_{rts} = -16.9 - 10 \log w + 10 \log f + 20 \log \Delta h_m + L_{ori} \quad (10)$$

In this expression, $\Delta h_m = 3 \cdot nf - Hms$, $L_{ori} = 4.0 - 0.114(\phi - 55)$ for angles between 55 and 90 (in degrees), and $w = b/2$, where b is the average distance between buildings. Note that Δh_m is the difference between the average height of buildings (considering 3 m per floor) and the mobile station antenna height, and L_{ori} is an empirical correction factor that takes into account the (average) orientation of the streets with respect to the incident wave. However, if additional information about the urban environment is not provided, the orientation angle ϕ is set to 90° as recommended.

The multi-screen loss L_{msd} can be evaluated via the following expression:

$$L_{msd} = L_{bsh} + k_a + k_d \log d + k_f \log f - 9 \log b \quad (11)$$

If $\Delta h_b = Hbs - 3 \cdot nf$ (difference between the base station antenna height and the average height of buildings), then, for $\Delta h_b > 0$, $L_{bsh} = -18 \log(1 + \Delta h_b)$, and $k_a = 54$ and $k_d = 18$. Finally, $k_f = -4 + 0.7 \left(\frac{f}{925} - 1 \right)$ for medium-size cities.

A summary of the variables used in the BN model is shown in Table 1.

B. BAYESIAN NETWORK LEARNING PROCESS

In the process of learning a BN, the following steps must be followed: i) *structural learning*, which will determine the topology of the BN or DAG, and ii) *parametric learning*, or estimation of conditional probabilities between nodes once the network topology is established.

TABLE 1. Description of the 11 features that make up the dataset used to learn the structure and parameters of the path-loss BN model.

Variable name	Description	Values
<i>Hbs</i>	Base station antenna height (m)	[30.0, 34.9], [34.9, 40.0], [40.0, 45.1], [45.1, 50.0]
<i>Hms</i>	Mobile station antenna height (m)	[1.0, 1.5], [1.5, 2.0], [2.0, 2.5], [2.5, 3.0]
<i>d</i>	Distance from base station (km)	[2.0, 2.8], [2.8, 3.5], [3.5, 4.3], [4.3, 5.0]
<i>f</i>	Frequency (MHz)	[800.1, 1097.3], [1097.3, 1390.1], [1390.1, 1698.2], [1698.2, 2000.0]
<i>nf</i>	Average number of floors	[0.35, 3.9], [3.9, 7.0], [7.0, 10.0], [10.0, 16.7]
<i>b</i>	Average distance between two buildings (m)	[20.0, 27.3], [27.3, 35.0], [35.0, 42.5], [42.5, 50.0]
<i>LU</i>	Path loss in urban areas (dB) for Okumura-Hata model	[196.3, 221.6], [221.6, 228.8], [228.8, 235.8], [235.8, 258.8]
<i>PLPhiladelphia</i>	Path loss in urban areas (dB) for Philadelphia Lee model	[128.5, 160.0], [160.0, 169.2], [169.2, 178.7], [178.7, 204.6]
<i>PLNewark</i>	Path loss in urban areas (dB) for Newark Lee model	[125.9, 159.4], [159.4, 170.2], [170.2, 180.1], [180.1, 207.3]
<i>PLTokyo</i>	Path loss in urban areas (dB) for Tokyo Lee model	[139.1, 168.5], [168.5, 177.3], [177.3, 185.4], [185.4, 209.8]
<i>PathLossCOST</i>	Path loss in urban areas (dB) COST 231-Walfish Ikegami	[181.8, 259.0], [259.0, 283.1], [283.1, 305.5], [305.5, 382.2]

FIGURE 1. DAG representing a possible structure of the path-loss BN model. It has been obtained through the *hc* learning algorithm (a search and score algorithm) of the *bnlearn* package in R.

1) STRUCTURAL LEARNING

The problem of discovering the causal structure becomes more complex as the number of variables increases [3], [5], [40]. Basically, two approaches to structural learning can be considered [8]: (i) *search-and-score* structure learning, and (ii) *constraint-based* structure learning. Algorithms based on search and score assign a number (score) to each BN, and then the BN structure with the highest score is selected. These algorithms are merely implementations of different general-purpose heuristic search techniques, such as hill-climbing, tabu search, simulated annealing, and various genetic algorithms.

Constraint-based search algorithms perform a set of conditional independence tests on the data [22], which are used to generate an undirected graph, and then additional independence tests must be considered to obtain the BN structure. The process includes three steps: (1) the undirected graph underlying the network structure is learned. Since an exhaustive search is computationally impractical for all but the simplest datasets, all learning algorithms rely on some form of optimization; (2) assign directions to all arcs that are part of a *v*-structure (e.g., connections of the type $A \rightarrow B \leftarrow C$); and finally, assign directions to the remaining arcs as needed to satisfy the acyclic constraint.

We used the package *bnlearn* [27], [37] of R language [34] to learn the structure. A *single best* model (as a possible model) was learned with *hill-climbing* (*hc*), a score-based algorithm which explores the search space starting from a network structure (usually the empty graph) and adding, deleting, or reversing one arc at a time until the score can no longer be improved (this process is also known as greedy search) (see Figure 1).

2) PARAMETRIC LEARNING

Given the network topology, we also executed the *bnlearn* package in R language to perform a Bayesian parameter estimation using the Dirichlet distribution [28] (through the *bayes* method included in that package). A conditional probability distribution was obtained for each node. An example of conditional probability distribution is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Table of conditional probabilities for the feature *nf* conditioned on its parent value, in this case the feature *Hbs* with its different intervals.

<i>Hbs</i>	<i>nf</i> 0.35-3.9	<i>nf</i> 3.9-7.0	<i>nf</i> 7.0-10.0	<i>nf</i> 10.0-16.7
30.0-34.9	0.3119	0.3055	0.3023	0.0804
34.9-40.0	0.2690	0.2754	0.2478	0.2078
40.0-45.1	0.2163	0.2359	0.2327	0.3151
45.1-50.0	0.2028	0.1832	0.2172	0.3968

C. PATH-LOSS BN GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION

Although the *bnlearn* package can be used to make inference, in order to have a clear graphical representation, we selected the Samiam package [36]. The model obtained with the *bnlearn* package can be loaded into the Samiam package and, once compiled, the path-loss BN model can be plotted as shown in Figure 2. The joint probability distribution of the path-loss BN in Figure 2 requires the specification of 11 conditional probability tables, one for each variable conditioned on the set of its parents. Each variable is represented by its set of possible states, for example, the variable distance (*d*) is in exactly one of the possible states: [2.0, 2.8], [2.8, 3.5], [3.5, 4.3], [4.3, 5.0]. Samiam calculates and displays the marginal probabilities instead of displaying the conditional probability distributions. Once the variables are instantiated (we observe that certain variables take a value), then for the remaining variables, their probabilities are updated and Samiam will

FIGURE 2. Path-loss BN model representing the relationships between features learned by sampling from the following empirical models: Okumura-Hata (LU), Lee (Philadelphia (PL-Philadelphia), Newark (PL-Newark), and Tokyo (PL-Tokyo)) and COST-231 Walfish-Ikegami. For each variable, the compiled BN model shows the marginal probabilities (expressed in percentage) as well as a summary of the original data distribution.

display the conditional probabilities of the variables given these instances.

D. VALIDATION OF THE BN

We validated the BN model using a 10-fold cross-validation for BN via a log-likelihood loss function. In Table 3, the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and the percentage correctly classified for the different features are shown.

E. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

We included other classification algorithms in order to have reference benchmarks for our BN (see Table 4); in particular, we included Naïve Bayes (NB), Logistic function, Multi-layer perceptron, and the J48 WEKA tree algorithms [47] integrated in Weka tool [11]. The performance of each classification model was evaluated using four statistical measures: accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and ROC area.

In addition, we also provide three statistics, obtained with Netica software, that evaluate the degree of fit between the model and the test data: logarithmic loss, quadratic loss, and spherical result [29]. The logarithmic loss varies between zero and infinity, where zero indicates the best goodness of fit. The quadratic loss varies between zero and two, where zero corresponds to the best execution, and, finally, the spherical payoff is bounded between zero and one, where one indicates a perfect fit between the model and the data. In Table 5, we note that the three metrics exhibit good alignment for all

output variables (LU, PLPhiladelphia, PLNewark, PLTokyo and PathLossCOST).

IV. RESULTS

BNs are used to make inferences, which implies that probabilities have to be updated when new information is introduced [4]. To infer, different reasoning patterns can be adopted [12], [18]: *causal reasoning* (from top to bottom), *evidential reasoning* (from bottom to top), and *inter-causal reasoning* (very close to human reasoning, occurs when different causes of the same effect can interact). Here, we are interested in applying *causal reasoning*. In particular, we are interested in obtaining the different variable states that maximize the estimated probability of the lowest values for the different path losses (*LU* in [196.3, 221.6], *PLPhiladelphia* in [128.5, 160.0], *PLNewark* in [125.9, 159.4], *PLTokyo* in [139.1, 168.5], and *PathLossCOST* in [181.8, 259.0]).

A. INCREASING THE ESTIMATED LIKELIHOOD OF THE LOWEST PATH LOSSES

To achieve the lowest path losses, variables are instantiated by first selecting those that most increase the estimated probability of each path loss at its lowest possible level. Figure 3 shows the different instances to obtain the lowest estimated probability value for *LU* path loss, similarly Figure 4 for *PLPhiladelphia* path loss, Figure 5 for *PLTokyo*

TABLE 3. Summary of the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and percentage correctly classified for the different features included in the BN. A 10-fold cross-validation is used.

Variable name	State	Accuracy	AUC
Hbs	30.0-34.9	0.6022	82.7456
Hbs	34.9-40.0	0.3070	62.0124
Hbs	40.0-45.1	0.2843	62.8464
Hbs	45.1-50.0	0.5260	79.1346
Hms	1.0-1.5	0.5565	83.2777
Hms	1.5-2.0	0.3644	66.9191
Hms	2.0-2.5	0.2613	64.4983
Hms	2.5-3.0	0.6036	83.8085
d	2.0-2.8	0.8858	96.3638
d	2.8-3.5	0.5333	88.5527
d	3.5-4.3	0.5024	85.1947
d	4.3-5.0	0.8021	93.5484
f	800.1-1097.3	0.5254	84.2305
f	1097.3-1390.1	0.4742	81.3560
f	1390.1-1698.2	0.7533	92.8143
f	1698.2-2000.0	0.8255	95.4379
b	20.0-27.3	0.2930	58.7297
b	27.3-35.0	0.2641	51.5391
b	35.0-42.5	0.3056	52.3589
b	42.5-50.0	0.2943	58.1147
nf	0.35-3.9	0.7504	92.5933
nf	3.9-7.0	0.7304	91.5658
nf	7.0-10.0	0.5412	82.5138
nf	10.0-16.7	0.5636	82.0802
LU	196.3-221.6	0.9226	99.0877
LU	221.6-228.6	0.8070	96.5803
LU	228.8-235.8	0.8389	97.0058
LU	235.8-258.8	0.9194	99.2373
PLPhiladelphia	128.5-160.0	0.9382	99.7287
PLPhiladelphia	160.0-169.2	0.8972	98.9647
PLPhiladelphia	169.2-178.7	0.9143	99.3556
PLPhiladelphia	178.7-204.6	0.9680	99.8950
PLTokyo	139.1-168.5	0.9446	99.4547
PLTokyo	168.5-177.3	0.8744	98.1497
PLTokyo	177.3-185.4	0.8923	98.4517
PLTokyo	185.4-209.8	0.9488	99.5325
PLNewark	125.9-159.4	0.9545	99.4520
PLNewark	159.4-170.2	0.8863	98.4132
PLNewark	170.2-180.1	0.9093	98.7604
PLNewark	180.1-207.3	0.9645	99.6051
PathLossCOST	181.8-259.0	0.8630	92.2042
PathLossCOST	259.0-283.1	0.5163	82.5796
PathLossCOST	283.1-305.5	0.5163	81.6295
PathLossCOST	305.5-382.2	0.6624	91.2033

path loss, Figure 6 for *PLNewark* path loss, and Figure 7 for *PathLossCOST* path loss. Figures 3 to 6 show similar behavior patterns where the features that most increase the path loss are *frequency* (in the range [800.1 – 1097.3]) and *distance* (in the range [2.0 – 2.8]), and achieving in step 2 an estimated probability of 0.9470 in the variable *LU*, 0.9931 in the variable *PLPhiladelphia*, 0.9875 in the variable *PLTokyo*, and 0.9944 in the variable *PLNewark*. Figure 7 shows a different pattern, as in this case the most influential feature is *nf* in the range [0.35–3.9], achieving an estimated probability of 0.6793, and an estimated probability of 0.9140 once *f* is instantiated in the range [800.1 – 1097.3] in step 2. So, in this case the features with the greatest influence to obtain the lowest path loss are the *average number of floors (nf)*

TABLE 4. Performance comparison between our BN and other machine learning methods for the different path-loss nodes. All methods are evaluated using a 10-fold cross-validation.

Algorithms	Path Loss node	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	ROC Area
Bayesian network	LU	92.26	0.9250	0.9636	0.9909
	PLPhiladelphia	93.82	0.9358	0.9816	0.9973
	PLTokyo	94.46	0.9450	0.9781	0.9945
	PLNewark	95.45	0.9565	0.9717	0.9945
	PathLossCOST	86.30	0.8682	0.7867	0.9220
Naïve Bayes	LU	76.68	0.8630	0.9220	0.9770
	PLPhiladelphia	92.78	0.9390	0.9850	0.9980
	PLTokyo	90.92	0.9330	0.9980	0.9960
	PLNewark	91.64	0.9300	0.998	0.9920
	PathLossCOST	63.06	0.6320	0.7910	0.8130
Logistic	LU	87.78	0.9200	0.9720	0.9800
	PLPhiladelphia	93.60	0.9390	0.9850	0.9980
	PLTokyo	92.980	0.9530	0.9860	0.9980
	PLNewark	93.81	0.9440	0.9860	0.9970
	PathLossCOST	76.64	0.6910	0.8990	0.9190
Multilayer Perceptron	LU	85.75	0.9080	0.9670	0.9880
	PLPhiladelphia	92.93	0.9460	0.982	0.9970
	PLTokyo	91.22	0.9480	0.9810	0.9930
	PLNewark	92.23	0.9420	0.9790	0.9940
	PathLossCOST	74.35	0.6660	0.8930	0.9000
J48	LU	87.38	0.9110	0.9720	0.9840
	PLPhiladelphia	93.22	0.9410	0.9820	0.9960
	PLTokyo	92.71	0.9550	0.985	0.9930
	PLNewark	93.81	0.9420	0.9880	0.9940
	PathLossCOST	74.02	0.6510	0.8930	0.8790

TABLE 5. Scoring results obtained with Netica. The degree of fit the BN model and the test data is obtained through three statistics: logarithmic loss, quadratic loss and spherical payoff.

Variable name	Logarithmic loss	Quadratic loss	Spherical payoff
d	0.5720	0.3678	0.7851
f	0.5131	0.3230	0.8103
Hms	0.8325	0.4865	0.6994
Hbs	0.8799	0.5082	0.6849
nf	0.4733	0.2957	0.8312
b	1.1290	0.6335	0.5953
LU	0.2231	0.1448	0.9188
PLPhiladelphia	0.0533	0.0340	0.9812
PLNewark	0.1229	0.0765	0.9577
PLTokyo	0.0785	0.4090	0.9727
PathLossCOST	0.3006	0.2008	0.8837

and the *frequency (f)*, while with the previous models the most influential variables were the *frequency (f)* and the *distance (d)*.

B. COMPARING THE DIFFERENT PATH LOSS

Figures 8 and 9 show the variability of the path loss for the different models when the input variables are instantiated. In Figure 8 the instances have been chosen taking into account the largest increase in the estimated probability for the variables of the Lee model and the LU model, while in Figure 9 the instantiations have been chosen considering the largest increase in the estimated probability for the path loss COST variable.

In Figure 8, a comparison of the evolution of the different path losses is shown. In step 1, the *frequency* is instantiated to the value [800.1 – 1097.3], achieving an estimated conditional probability of 0.6026 for *LU*,

FIGURE 3. The probability of the variable *LU* in its four different states is updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *LU*, step 1 = *f* at state 800.1-1097.3, step 2 = *d* at state 2.0-2.8, step 3 = *Hms* at state 2.0-2.5 or *Hms* at state 2.5-3.0 or *Hbs* at state 45.1-50.0. The successive steps are plotted on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for *LU* at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

FIGURE 5. The probability of the variable *PLTokyo* in its four different states is updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PLTokyo*, step 1 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 2 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 3 = *Hms* in state 2.0-2.5 or *Hms* in state 2.5-3.0 or *Hbs* in state 40.0-45.1 or 45.1-50.0. The successive steps are plotted on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for *PLTokyo* at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

FIGURE 4. The probability of the variable *PLPhiladelphia* in its four different states is updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PLPhiladelphia*, step 1 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 2 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 3 = *Hms* in state 2.0-2.5 or *Hms* in state 2.5-3.0 or *Hbs* in state 40.0-45.1 or 45.1-50.0. The successive steps are plotted on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for *PLPhiladelphia* at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

FIGURE 6. The probability of the variable *PLNewark* in its four different states is updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PLNewark*, step 1 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 2 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 3 = *Hms* in state 2.0-2.5 or *Hms* in state 2.5-3.0 or *Hbs* in state 40.0-45.1 or 45.1-50.0. The successive steps are plotted on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for *PLNewark* at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

0.5220 for *PLPhiladelphia*, 0.5756 for *PLTokyo*, 0.4820 for *PLNewark*, and 0.4072 for *PathLossCOST*. In step 2, the *distance* is instantiated to the value [2.0-2.5], and the estimated conditional probability becomes 0.9470 for *LU*, 0.9931 for *PLPhiladelphia*, 0.9875 for *PLTokyo*, 0.9944 for *PLNewark*, and 0.512 for *PathLossCOST*. Then, in step 3, either *Hms* is instantiated to [2.0-2.5] or [2.5 - 3.0], or *Hbs* is instantiated to [45.1 - 50.0] for all path loss variables or to [40.0 - 45.1] for all path loss variables, achieving an estimated conditional probability of 1 in all path loss variables

except *PathLossCOST*, which becomes 49.11. So this last case shows a clearly different pattern of behavior.

The variables *b* and *nf* are specific to the *PathLossCOST* model, therefore, in step 4 of Figure 7, *b* is instantiated at [42.5 - 50.0], achieving an estimated conditional probability of 0.5503, and, in step 5, *nf* is instantiated at [0.35 - 3.9], achieving an estimated conditional probability of 1. This is only for the *PathLossCOST* variables, as the remaining path losses do not modify their behavior. Steps 4 and 5 of

FIGURE 7. The probability of the variable *PathLossCOST* in its four different states is updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PathLossCOST*, step 1 = *nf* in state 0.35-3.9, step 2 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 3 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 4 = *b* in state 42.5-50.0 or *Hbs* in state 45.0-50.0 or *Hms* in state 1.5-2.0 or *Hms* in state 2.5-3.0. The successive steps are plotted on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for *PathLossCOST* at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

FIGURE 9. Probabilities of the different path loss models (Okumura-Hata, Lee (Philadelphia, Newark, and Tokyo), and COST 231-Walfish Ikegami) at states ([196.3-221.6], [125.9-159.4], [128.5-160.0], [139.1-168.5], and [181.8-259.0] respectively). These probabilities are updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PathLossCOST*, step 1 = *nf* in state 0.35-3.9, step 2 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 3 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 4 = *b* in state 35.0-42.5, and step 5 = *Hbs* in state 40.0-45.1.0 or 45.1-50.0 or *Hms* in state 2.0-2.5 or 2.5-3.0. The successive steps are represented on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for the different path loss variables at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

FIGURE 8. Probabilities of the different path loss models (Okumura-Hata, Lee (Philadelphia, Newark, and Tokyo), and COST 231-Walfish Ikegami) at states ([196.3-221.6], [125.9-159.4], [128.5-160.0], [139.1-168.5], and [181.8-259.0] respectively). These probabilities are updated in different steps as new evidence is introduced. The different steps are: step 0 = initial conditional probability of *PathLossCOST*, step 1 = *f* in state 800.1-1097.3, step 2 = *d* in state 2.0-2.8, step 3 = *Hbs* in state 40.0-45.1.0 or 45.1-50.0 or *Hms* in state 2.0-2.5 or 2.5-3.0, step 4 = *b* in state 42.5-50.0, and step 5 = *nf* in state 0.35-3.9. The successive steps are represented on the horizontal axis, while the estimated probability for the different path loss variables at different levels is shown on the vertical axis.

Figure 8 are not considered in Figures 3-6 because they have no influence on their corresponding path losses.

Figure 9 also shows a comparison of the evolution of the different path losses, but in this case the instantiations at each step are those that most rapidly increase the probability

of the variable *PathLossCOST* at a low level. In step 1, when *nf* is instantiated to [0.35 – 3.9], the corresponding estimated conditional probabilities are 0.6793, 0.2376, 0.2378, 0.2400 and 0.2352, respectively for the variables *PathLossCOST*, *PLPhiladelphia*, *PLTokyo*, *PLNewark* and *LU*. In step 2, *f* is instantiated to [800.1 – 1097.3], and the corresponding estimated conditional probabilities are 0.9140, 0.5076, 0.5568, 0.4701 and 0.5753 for *PathLossCOST*, *PLPhiladelphia*, *PLTokyo*, *PLNewark* and *LU*, respectively. The instantiation of *distance* in step 3 increases all path losses, resulting in conditional probabilities of 0.9973, 0.9916, 0.9846, 0.9930 and 0.9364, respectively for the variables *PathLossCOST*, *PLPhiladelphia*, *PLTokyo*, *PLNewark* and *LU*. In step 4, when *b* is instantiated to [35.0 – 42.5], *PathLossCOST* achieves a conditional probability of 1 at its lowest value while the remaining path losses are invariant. Finally, in step 5, all variables achieve a conditional probability of 1 at their lowest value.

V. DISCUSSION

Our study is a first experiment which shows the suitability of BNs in cellular network planning, in this case for small or medium-size cities. By considering BNs, practitioners can achieve more accurate, flexible and insightful path loss predictions, enhancing the planning and optimization of wireless communication systems. Furthermore, BNs often outperform other benchmarking models in certain scenarios, as appears to be the case in cellular network planning (see Table 4). This is due to several key strengths and

advantages: (1) They may incorporate uncertainty in both the data and relationships between variables, this makes BNs more flexible and robust in real-world applications, where data is often noisy or incomplete; (2) Their graphical representation of dependencies between variables provides a highly interpretable model; (3) BNs capture the relationships between variables learning a structure that gives a distinct advantage over other models that may only capture correlations without an explicit representation of how variables influence each other; (4) Bayesian networks can model complex dependencies between variables that other models might struggle with, especially when variables are not independent. Other models, like neural networks, might outperform BNs in terms of raw prediction accuracy in large datasets, but they generally lack the interpretability and flexibility that BNs offer when working with uncertain or limited data.

BNs provide a structured way to perform probabilistic inference, helping planners predict outcomes such as network performance under different configurations and traffic conditions. This is critical for optimizing network parameters. The path loss BN model showed the features with highest influence in the different path losses: Okumura-Hata, Lee and COST 231-Walfish Ikegami. Furthermore, BNs can quantify uncertainties inherent in cellular planning, such as fluctuating traffic patterns, interference levels, and equipment failures, whenever these features are considered in the BN model. Specifically, in our model we only considered the following features: *base station antenna height*, *mobile station antenna height*, *distance* and *frequency* for all path losses, and *average number of floors* and *average distance between two buildings* for *PathLossCOST* variable. This would allow for more robust and reliable planning.

BNs can be trained and updated with new data, improving their accuracy over time. This is particularly useful for adaptive network planning in dynamic environments where conditions change frequently. Due to the lack of data (these have been generated), the path loss BN model presented here is static and thus it constitutes a first step; however, it can be modified and adapted to a dynamic environment by learning from new data.

One important advantage is that BNs support decision-making by providing probabilistic insights into the impact of different planning choices. For example, they can help determine the best locations for new base stations or the optimal configuration of existing infrastructure to maximize coverage and capacity. Moreover, BNs can assess the risks associated with different planning strategies, allowing for more informed decisions that balance performance improvements with potential downsides. Therefore, planners can use BNs to conduct scenario analysis, exploring the effects of various changes or unexpected events (like a sudden increase in user demand or a new interference source) on network performance. By understanding the probabilistic relationships between different network parameters, BNs can

help in optimizing resource allocation to improve overall network efficiency.

The path loss BN model allows us to determine those features with the strongest influence in obtaining the lowest path loss. While the Lee and Okumura-Hata models determined the same critical features (*frequency* and *distance*), the COST 231-Walfish Ikegami showed that the *average number of floors per building* and *frequency* were the most relevant factors.

Overall, the application of BNs in cellular network planning enhances the ability to make data-driven, probabilistic-based informed decisions, leading to better performance, reliability, and adaptability of the network.

On the other hand, one of the points highlighted in the paper is the applicability of the BN approach to emerging or future 5G/6G scenarios. In this sense, a significant challenge is that 5G/6G cellular networks are being designed to operate in the millimeter wave (mmWave) frequency band, because it offers an unprecedentedly huge transmission bandwidth. However, signals transmitted in this band are subject to new sources of degradation, namely severe blocking, rain attenuation, atmospheric absorption and light pollution (as a form of interference), which are not considered by classical empirical propagation models. These models, such as the ones considered in this paper, were developed from measurements taken in the microwave frequency band used by previous generations of cellular networks (up to 4G), and are therefore no longer appropriate for predicting the behavior of mmWave signals. This is especially true for indoor scenarios, where features such as building materials, characterized by their penetration losses, and furniture layout become highly relevant. Therefore, significant research activity is currently underway aimed at developing propagation models for 5G/6G cellular networks. This problem is being addressed from different perspectives. Some works rely heavily on measurements. For example, in [46], extensive channel measurements are performed in 5G scenarios to statistically characterize the delay spread. In [21], a measurement-based correction of traditional wireless propagation models is proposed. Other contributions are [35], which compares ray-tracing with other 5G propagation models, [23], where a map-based method satisfying the requirements of 5G propagation models is presented, and [41], which compares two well-known propagation models for 5G, namely the alpha-beta-gamma (ABG) model and the close-in (CI) model. Finally, there are also very good surveys on wireless propagation models for 5G, such as [30] and [42]. It should be noted that all these contributions are about 5G and not 5G and 6G, but we can expect 5G models to be valid or easily extensible to 6G cellular networks. An alternative to all these approaches for modeling propagation in the next generations of cellular networks is to build a BN model. However, to perform this task optimally, new input variables and new datasets obtained from real measurements rather than virtual data are required.

Using a BN to model wireless propagation is not without difficulties and limitations, which can basically be summarized in the availability of real data and scalability. Both aspects are discussed in the following subsections.

A. AVAILABILITY OF REAL DATA

The construction of an accurate BN requires substantial and high-quality data. Inadequate or poor-quality data can lead to inaccurate models and unreliable inferences, which can negatively impact planning decisions. In this sense, our study presents limitations in terms of data availability, since the measurements that support the different propagation models considered are not published. We have therefore created a virtual dataset by uniformly sampling the input variables in compatible regions for all models. This virtual dataset may introduce biases that do not fully reflect real-world scenarios. Nevertheless, this limitation does not compromise the technical integrity of the model, but rather indicates the need for further validation and adjustments with real data.

In the future, real data could be provided by the research community or by mobile network operators or both. However, in the case of mobile operators, privacy issues could arise that could compromise the richness of the final dataset. To address this, formal collaboration between academic research groups and industrial partners, through publicly or privately funded projects, would be a good alternative. Considering the continuous investment of mobile operators in expanding and upgrading their networks, developing a powerful AI tool such as a Bayesian Network (BN) for network planning would benefit this industrial sector as a whole. Such collaborations have begun to become a reality in the aforementioned mmWave band, as several university-industry research consortia have recently been formed to collaborate on field measurements, knowledge sharing, and the production of empirical models. From the perspective of the BN modeling process, the databases developed by these groups could be used again to create a BN model for mmWave propagation. The optimal situation would be that these databases were publicly available or at least accessible after requesting permission.

B. SCALABILITY

Scalability is another important aspect of the modeling approach proposed in this paper. This can be considered from different points of view. One refers to its inherent graphical representation. In this regard, a minor limitation of the BN approach is that as the network grows in size and complexity, it can become more difficult to interpret and understand, which in turn can hinder the ability of stakeholders to explain and justify planning decisions.

A more critical factor in scalability appears to be the higher network density expected in urban areas as a result of 5G/6G technologies. In this sense, we believe that higher network densities will impact the scalability of network deployment, as mobile operators usually deal with this problem by

adapting cell sizes (in other words, a higher number of smaller cells and base stations would increase deployment costs). However, we do not believe that network density alone (in terms of users or devices per unit area) will impact the scalability of the BN model, because the learning process involved is based on data (field measurements) obtained from a given area, but not on the number of users/devices to be served in this area. Certainly, what impacts the scalability of a BN model is the number of variables and the amount of data considered in the learning process. In the case of millimeter wave propagation, the number of variables would definitely increase, because penetration losses of building materials, furniture arrangement and other factors would become very important, as we stated before. However, scalability becomes an issue in BN when dealing with hundreds of variables, which seems not to be the case, although, even in this case, several approaches proposed in the literature, as well as the availability of specialized software tools, can efficiently manage the different stages (data loading, structural learning, parameter learning) of building a complex BN [48].

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a machine learning approach to manage the uncertainty derived from the variety of empirical propagation models used in cellular network planning processes. This approach is based on training a Bayesian network model from virtual data generated by sampling the Okumura-Hata, Lee and COST 231 Walfish-Ikegami propagation models, in their versions for small and medium-size cities. As mentioned, BNs provide a structured way to perform probabilistic inferences that, in the present context, helps practitioners achieve more accurate predictions about path loss.

Due to the unavailability of real data from which the aforementioned empirical models were developed, we have sampled these models to create a virtual dataset to train the BN. This approach does not in any way distort the essential objective of this work, as the virtual dataset emulates real data. However, to further improve the reliability of the proposed BN model, future work could consist of updating it by adding virtual data from other propagation models and using real data from live network measurements taken in multiple scenarios. These data would be integrated with available virtual data to train a new and updated BN.

Finally, with the upcoming 5G/6G scenarios, there is now a great opportunity to build a new path loss BN model, this time focusing on the mmWave frequency band.

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